

NON-DESTRUCTIVE ASSESSMENT OF PROPERTIES OF PULTRUDED GFRP SUBJECT TO HYGROTHERMAL AGING

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ABSTRACT

Despite having great weather resistance, glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) degradation was observed after years of exposure in the field. The use of non-destructive tests shows a good alternative to evaluate the integrity of this material. Thus, this work used free vibration tests through frequency response to detect damage in GFRP aged in chambers with controlled temperature, humidity and salinity. Through the evaluation of the natural frequencies, the impact of environmental conditions on the integrity of the material was observed.

KEYWORDS

Experimental dynamic analysis; Non-destructive test; Aging

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, pultruded fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) members have attracted great interest in the construction industry due to their high strength-to-weight ratio and their applicability in aggressive environments (Liao et al., 1999; Liu et al., 2020; Sousa et al., 2019). The possibility of tailoring properties by combining a polymer matrix such as polyester, epoxy, vinyl ester and fibers such as aramid, basalt, carbon and glass also allows the material to achieve a desired performance with accessible cost (Grammatikos et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2020; Vedernikov et al., 2020). However, despite FRP's superior corrosion resistance, reduction of mechanical properties can also be observed when exposed to harsh environments (Liao et al., 1999; Liu et al., 2020; Selzer & Friedrich, 1995; Sousa et al., 2019).

Among the environmental scenarios that affect the behavior, immersion in water, occurrence of freezing/thawing or wetting/drying cycles and exposure to high relative humidity (RH), alkaline and acidic solutions, high and low temperatures, UV rays can be highlighted (Liu et al., 2020). Combinations of such scenarios may also occur, leading to coupled degradation phenomena. The so-called hygrothermal aging is characterized by the combination effects produced by temperature and immersion in water or exposure to high RH along, which has already been the subject of several works (Liu et al., 2020; Selzer & Friedrich, 1995, 1997).

The mechanisms of water uptake in FRP material reduces the material mechanical properties by chemical and physical degradation processes such as plasticization and hydrolysis (Grammatikos et al., 2016; Liao et al., 1999; Liu et al., 2020; Selzer & Friedrich, 1997). In saline environments, the water absorption process is similar to distilled water, with the presence of salt reducing the saturation equilibrium (Zafar et al., 2012). Furthermore, it is well-known that diffusion is a thermally activated process, so the FRP exposure to a higher temperature accelerates the water uptake and the degradation effects caused by water (Selzer & Friedrich, 1997). Another relevant phenomenon related to temperature is the polymer post-cure, which increases mechanical properties to a certain extent before degradation occurs.

Regarding the structural damage monitoring, the use of experimental modal analysis consists in a promising alternative and has gained attention and acceptance among civil engineers (Kessler et al., 2002; Rodrigues Gaspar et al., 2021; Tam et al., 2017). Already widespread in the monitoring of the health of structures with isotropic materials such as steel (Carden & Fanning, 2004), the method based

on natural frequencies has already accurately evidenced damage in orthotropic or transversely isotropic materials (Montalvao, 2006). On the other hand, for the best of authors knowledge, the applicability of this technique to the monitoring of hygrothermally aged pultruded FRP structures is still unknown.

Thus, the objective of this work is to evaluate the degradation of pultruded FRP profiles aged in salt spray chambers under two different temperatures through free vibration tests. To accomplish this task, experimental dynamic analysis was performed using a piezoelectric hammer and an accelerometer to evaluate a full member response in terms of its natural frequencies.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Material Properties

The material used for the experimental tests consists of pultruded glass-fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) made of vinyl ester resin and E-Glass fibers. The specimens were extracted from an angle section with dimensions 101.6 mm x 6.35 mm (leg size x thickness) provided by the company Cogumelo© and previously characterized (Table 1) (Cardoso & Togashi, 2018).

Table 1: Properties for the pultruded GFRP material used in the study

Property	Unit	Value
Fiber volume content, V_f	%	33.9 ± 6.2
Tensile modulus in longitudinal direction, $E_{L,t}$	GPa	27.8 ± 2.5
Tensile strength in longitudinal direction, $F_{L,t}$	MPa	360 ± 26
Compressive modulus in longitudinal direction, $E_{L,c}$	GPa	30.4 ± 4.7
Compressive strength in longitudinal direction, $F_{L,c}$	MPa	286 ± 84
Flexural modulus in longitudinal direction, $E_{L,f}$	GPa	20.1 ± 1.3
Flexural modulus in transverse direction, $E_{T,f}$	GPa	8.60 ± 0.80
Shear modulus, G_{LT}	GPa	2.47 ± 0.40

Hygrothermal Aging

The hygrothermal aging was conducted using walk-in salt-spray chambers manufactured by Equilam, as shown in Figure 1. The chambers, built with insulating fiber-polymer composite walls, work by injecting a saline solution into its interior through the Venturi effect, generating a high temperature sea air effect.

The aging was performed in two different chambers, working at medium temperatures of $35.6 \pm 0.4^\circ\text{C}$ and $60.9 \pm 6.8^\circ\text{C}$ (thereafter referred as 35°C and 70°C). The relative humidity was also controlled during the aging period, remaining around 90 and 100%. The saline solution used was prepared by adding sodium chloride with an impurity tolerance of 0.3% for a NaCl concentration varying between 4% and 6%, according to the ASTM B117 recommendations (ASTM B117, 2019).

The specimens used in each test remained conditioned in the chambers for a total 136 days. At intermediate ages of 33 and 66 days, specimens were taken out of the chamber for experimental dynamic analysis. While outside the chambers, the specimens remained wrapped with plastic film to avoid moisture loss, only removed during the tests. Before testing, all the samples had their surface gently dried with a paper towel.

Regarding the storage of the samples inside the chambers, four small coupons were made, two from each leg having their length parallel to pultrusion direction and measuring 110 mm x 28 mm x 6.4 mm (length x width x thickness). The specimens were then positioned on shelves made of pultruded GFRP material. In the meanwhile, full angle members to be analyzed through experimental dynamic analysis were hung by strings, keeping their corner facing upwards to prevent accumulation of water and salt.

a)

b)

Figure 1: Walk-in salt spray chambers used for hygrothermal aging: a) overview; b) view of specimen accommodated inside chamber

Experimental Dynamic Analysis

Specimen Preparation

For the experimental dynamic analysis tests, 800-mm long angle specimens were extracted from the pultruded GFRP profiles provided by the manufacturer, in a total of two specimens, one for each aging chamber, labeled 1-35°C and 2-70°C.

Experimental Procedure

To characterize the free-free condition, the beams were hung using elastics with low rigidity, as reported in previous studies (García-Palacios et al., 2014; Ismael et al., 2018). This strategy reduces the influence of the supports on the response. The elastic hooks were fixed under the stiff floor of the Laboratory of Structures and Materials of the Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro. The elastics were rolled up and attached about 6 cm from the ends of the specimens, as shown in Figure 2.

a)

b)

Figure 2: Experimental dynamic analysis test setup: a) overview; b) detail of hooks and sensors

To perform the free vibration test, 126 impact points were marked on the specimen. Each point was excited three times, thus obtaining the mean frequency response function (FRF) for each one (Anders Brandt, 2011). As seen in Figure 2, impacts on the horizontal and vertical angles were performed using a piezoelectric hammer PCB Piezotronics 086C03 and the results in terms of accelerations were captured by a uniaxial PCB 333B40 accelerometer facing the z axis (in the direction of gravity). The signals were acquired through the cDAQ-9174 acquisition system from National Instruments (NI), equipped with the NI 9233 module with a sampling frequency of 2000 Hz. ARTeMIS software (ARTeMIS modal pro, 2019) was used for data pre and pos processing.

RESULTS

Physical Appearance of Specimens

The impacts of the aggressive environment on the physical appearance of the specimens can be observed in Figures 3 and 4. After 33 days of aging, the elements exhibited changes in their colors, caused by the oxidation of the resin. Despite the stains in the 1-35°C profile being more delimited, due to the presence of condensed water and oxidation, the 2-70°C profile showed a more homogeneous hue change, losing brightness and getting a coppery color. After 136 days of aging, significant changes are observed, mainly in the specimens exposed to 70°C. In addition to the high degree of oxidation, a significant accumulation of salt crystals was observed, something not observed for the milder temperature. It must be highlighted that the localized rust stains were not caused by aging itself, but by contact with condensed water carrying corrosion products.

Figure 3: Presence of high oxidation and salt crystallization on the surface of the aged profile at 70°C and 136 days

Figure 4: Tone comparison of profiles over 136 days at a) 35°C and b) 70°C

Moisture Absorption

The moisture uptake with aging time for each specimen is presented in Figure 5. For the specimens aged at 35°C, there was an almost linear gain in mass, representing an absorption of water at a practically constant rate up to 66 days, followed by an almost stable plateau, indicating that the material is approaching its saturation content. In addition, the greater absorption of 35°C-2 specimen compared to 35°C-1 specimen can be explained by the lower density of the element, which corresponds to a higher resin volume content in its composition.

Figure 5: Moisture uptake with time for different aging conditions

For specimens aged at 70 °C, a more pronounced absorption was observed, represented by the fast gain of mass up to 33 days. Between 33 and 66 days, a plateau is evident, which can be defined as the saturation point. In addition, the highest absorption was also evidenced in the specimen with the lowest specific mass, as well as the specimens submitted to the mildest chamber. Between 66 and 136 days, a mass reduction could be observed, indicating dissolution or material loss due to hydrolysis (Grammatikos et al., 2016; Liao et al., 1999). A noteworthy observation is depicted by the 70°C-4 and 35°C-2 specimens, wherein they reach saturation with nearly identical amounts of absorbed water. Due to their similar specific mass, the elevated temperature within the 70°C chamber accelerates the saturation of the 70°C-4 compared to that of 35°C-2. Consequently, both specimens ultimately reach an approximate equal value of 2.00%, as indicated by the dashed line.

Results obtained in the experimental modal analysis

When analyzing the effects of aging on the 1-35°C profile through dynamic tests, little change was observed in the dynamic behavior of the specimen (Figure 6). There was, however, a reduction in frequencies in almost all modes for 33 days, 66 days and 136 days of aging, represented by the shift of the graph to the left (red curve in the graph in Figure 6). At 66 and 136 days, there is a more constant behavior, where part of the stiffness was slightly restored, indicating the possibility of the influence of the post-cure effect. In Figure 6, it should be noted that, for signal processing purposes, the tests were conducted using a force window to reduce noise in force signals, except for the frequency response over 33 days. Although the amplitude (red curve) was shifted upwards when comparing this result with the other days, the estimation of the natural frequencies was not impaired.

During aging, several phenomena occur in the material simultaneously, such as loss of rigidity and mass caused by hydrolysis, volumetric expansion, creation of cracks and plasticization, and increase in rigidity associated with the post-curing effect. In general, although there was an increase in stiffness evidenced mainly after 33 days, it was not enough to completely restore or increase the original properties of the material, showing that degradation could be observed through this dynamic test, despite the greater variation of frequencies being 2.44% in relation to the original profile and a MAPE (Mean absolute percentage error), through equation (1), of 1.32%.

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{n=1}^{n=15} \left| \frac{f_i^{aged} - f_i^{unaged}}{f_i^{unaged}} \right| \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where n is the number of modes, f_i^{intact} is the unaged frequency and f_i^{aged} is the aged frequency.

As for the 2-70°C profile, there was a more evident variation in frequencies after 33 days of vibration aging (Figure 7). In the first removal of the chamber, there were reductions of up to 8.08% in frequencies and a MAPE of 3.9% showing the significant impact on this dynamic property and change in the elastic properties of the material. Between 66 days and 136 days, restoration of dynamic properties is also observed, as seen previously, up to a MAPE of 1.81%. A more accentuated restoration can be generated by the greater post-cure effect where the chamber had a temperature closer to the Tg of the resin.

Comparing the MAPE for the first 7 modes obtained for the 1-35°C and 2-70°C profile, a value of 1.59% and 4.96% was found, respectively. As for the last 8 modes, a variation of 1.09% and 2.97% was found, showing that the former was more impacted by the loss of stiffness of the composite. Table 2 presents fifteen natural frequencies (Hz) and the percentual change (%) of the aged condition to the unaged one for both profiles. It is worth noting that the influence of mass absorption on the natural frequencies due to absorption was minor. The frequency changes caused by the absorption of 3.25% of water (worst specimen at 70°C) had a 1.6% impact on the frequency values. Since most of the changes exceeded this value, it is possible to directly relate the frequency change to a change in stiffness. Similarly, at 35°C, the absorption of about 2% have an impact of up to 1.0% on the natural frequencies.

Figure 6: Frequency response function for unaged and aged 1-35°C profile

Figure 7: Frequency response function for unaged and aged 2-70°C profile

Table 2: Natural frequencies (Hz) and percentual change (%) for both profiles

Natural frequencies for unaged and aged 1-35°C profile					Natural frequencies for unaged and aged 2-70°C profile				
Mode	Unaged	33 days	66 days	136 days	Mode	Unaged	33 days	66 days	136 days
1	66,78 Hz	66,56 Hz -0,33%	66,84 Hz 0,09%	66,19 Hz -0,88%	1	67,11 Hz	63,50 Hz -5,38%	63,82 Hz -4,90%	65,19 Hz -2,86%
2	114,45 Hz	111,68 Hz -2,42%	112,79 Hz -1,45%	113,15 Hz -1,14%	2	112,39 Hz	107,30 Hz -4,53%	106,22 Hz -5,49%	108,73 Hz -3,26%
3	193,52 Hz	190,82 Hz -1,40%	190,40 Hz -1,61%	190,79 Hz -1,41%	3	194,20 Hz	186,54 Hz -3,94%	188,23 Hz -3,07%	190,55 Hz -1,88%
4	235,56 Hz	232,40 Hz -1,34%	232,56 Hz -1,27%	233,11 Hz -1,04%	4	236,62 Hz	217,50 Hz -8,08%	223,25 Hz -5,65%	231,28 Hz -2,26%
5	251,76 Hz	247,24 Hz -1,80%	247,93 Hz -1,52%	246,14 Hz -2,23%	5	248,32 Hz	236,27 Hz -4,85%	238,21 Hz -4,07%	247,43 Hz -0,36%
6	263,72 Hz	257,47 Hz -2,37%	263,10 Hz -0,24%	262,80 Hz -0,35%	6	258,47 Hz	246,30 Hz -4,71%	248,38 Hz -3,90%	251,97 Hz -2,51%
7	297,70 Hz	293,26 Hz -1,49%	294,04 Hz -1,23%	293,45 Hz -1,43%	7	296,04 Hz	286,52 Hz -3,22%	287,66 Hz -2,38%	290,98 Hz -1,71%
8	309,9 Hz	302,35 Hz -2,44%	304,20 Hz -1,84%	305,43 Hz -1,44%	8	305,90 Hz	292,99 Hz -4,22%	295,28 Hz -3,47%	299,14 Hz -2,21%
9	394,23 Hz	389,89 Hz -1,10%	389,73 Hz -1,14%	388,98 Hz -1,33%	9	390,51 Hz	376,65 Hz -3,55%	379,46 Hz -2,83%	385,48 Hz -1,29%
10	426,95 Hz	422,93 Hz -0,94%	423,71 Hz -0,76%	422,96 Hz -0,93%	10	426,03 Hz	413,37 Hz -2,97%	414,82 Hz -2,63%	418,68 Hz -1,73%
11	515,41 Hz	509,51 Hz -1,14%	510,96 Hz -0,86%	509,67 Hz -1,11%	11	513,01 Hz	496,64 Hz -3,19%	498,76 Hz -2,78%	504,91 Hz -1,58%
12	529,84 Hz	532,19 Hz 0,44%	531,44 Hz 0,30%	529,37 Hz -0,09%	12	532,16 Hz	521,93 Hz -1,92%	522,57 Hz -1,80%	526,88 Hz -0,99%
13	583,21 Hz	578,34 Hz -0,84%	579,47 Hz -0,64%	578,75 Hz -0,76%	13	584,81 Hz	568,79 Hz -2,74%	570,23 Hz -2,49%	575,39 Hz -1,61%
14	667,52 Hz	660,50 Hz -1,05%	662,40 Hz -0,77%	660,89 Hz -0,99%	14	667,95 Hz	648,26 Hz -2,95%	650,36 Hz -2,63%	656,67 Hz -1,69%
15	769,33 Hz	763,67 Hz -0,74%	765,63 Hz -0,48%	765,10 Hz -0,55%	15	768,96 Hz	751,64 Hz -2,25%	752,78 Hz -2,10%	759,68 Hz -1,21%

CONCLUSION

This work, through experimental modal analysis, aimed to evaluate the degradation in pultruded FRP profiles submitted to aging at temperature, salinity and high humidity. For this, the free-free configuration was used for the beams in the free vibration test, where the single-input, single-output method was adopted using an instrumented dynamic hammer and an accelerometer.

In the study of the absorption of the specimens, it was observed that the high temperature increases the absorption of water, that is, it makes the material reach saturation faster. This characteristic was evidenced, since specimens with the same specific mass, but placed in different chambers (35°C and 70°C), reached the same saturation level but at different times. In addition, specimens with lower specific mass absorbed a greater amount of moisture, since they had less fiber volume and possibly a greater amount of voids in their structure. Finally, there was a sharp drop in mass after saturation in the elements of the 70°C chamber, which could be explained by the hydrolysis of the matrix.

Regarding the variation of frequencies during aging, a reduction of this dynamic property was generally observed for the profiles of the chamber at 35°C and 70°C. The milder chamber presented smaller variations, reaching an MAPE of 1.32% and a greater variation of 2.44% in relation to the original profile. After the first removal, an increase in frequencies was observed, but this was not enough to reach the initial properties, which could be a result of the post-cure effect. In the 70°C chamber, more significant variations were obtained with MAPE of 3.9% and greater variation between modes of 8.08%. An increase in frequencies was also observed after the initial drop, which was not sufficient to restore control frequencies.

In general, the experiments showed that at 33 days of aging, the tests showed a reduction in stiffness followed by the restoration of properties after this period up to 136 days. Despite this, the subsequent gain in stiffness was not enough to reach the initial properties of the material.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.